

Evaluating and Studying of the Impact of Organizational Culture on Organizational Effectiveness

(Case Study: employees of Company of Electricity Distribution of Sistan and Baluchestan)

Author's Details:

Ebrahim Haddadi-Assistant professor in public Administration, College of human science, Zahehan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Zahedan, Iran

Shima Lakzaei-Graduate student of public Administration, College of human science, Zahehan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Zahedan, Iran

Abstract

Due to recent changes in structures of organizations, effectiveness in organizations has been considered more. For this reason, in this study we have tried to identify the effective factors of effectiveness to specify their roles in improving of effectiveness in the organizations. The main goal of this study is studying of the impact of organizational culture on organizational effectiveness; the statistical population of this research is employees of Company of Electricity Distribution of Sistan and Baluchestan who were selected as statistical sample through Morgan table. The method of data collection in theory is library method and in testing of hypotheses is survey method. The results of the research show that tribal culture and market have a significant and direct impact on organizational effectiveness and hierarchical culture also have an adverse effect on organizational effectiveness.

Keywords: organizational effectiveness, organizational culture, hierarchical culture, market culture, tribal culture

Introduction

Organizational culture as a powerful and real phenomenon has penetrated into all aspects of the organization and plays an essential role in achieving the goals and strategies of the companies. Existing of common identity, beliefs, values and normative behavior among members of organization, cause integration in efforts, commitment within the organization and a clear understanding of the existential philosophy and direction of its actions and as a result will cause the success of the organization (Ardalan, 2008:36).

Organizational culture is a source of sustainable competitive advantage. In today's highly competitive world, companies are using of their resources to provide services and thus will give the value to their products which will lead to a competitive advantage. A culture which give value to both external focus (such as improving the competitive position) and internal focus (e.g. social technical systems), may maximize the efficient use of innovation (Oke, 2007).

Effectiveness is an overall concept which its increasing as a crucial need is always been considered by scholars and thinkers for improving the lives of people, activities and organizations and its goal is to build a better community for all countries of the world and it is more than two decades which has become one of the most important concerns of managers. Organizational effectiveness in today's competitive world, as a point of view, forms the most important goal of the organizations and has been located in the organizational literature of all schools deeply. For example, the thinkers of classical school considered issues such as, maximizing of production or reducing of the cost as effectiveness. Some believed that effectiveness was caused by the satisfaction of the employees and some considered the human needs and self-actualization in the end and as a result will effect on sense of belonging, commitment and loyalty of the staffs to the organization and finally will have a positive impact on the amount of effectiveness (Haghi, 2006).

The hypothesis of the research

Organizational culture has a significant impact on the organizational effectiveness of the company of Electricity Distribution of Sistan and Baluchestan.

Theories

The organizational effectiveness

The effectiveness of the organization is the degree or the extent which the organization will achieve its desired objectives. The effectiveness of the organization is a degree which an organization will meet its goal without wearing out its members and community and by using of special resources without wasting its resources. In fact, organizational effectiveness shows the degree of proximity of an organization to its goals (Zahedi, 2009, 269). Or it is the degree which an organization will achieve its goal (Omidi and et al, 2012, 78).

The organizational culture

The concept of culture

The concept of culture is the quality of life of a group of human beings who will transfer from one generation to another.

The organizational culture

In today's turbulent world, the success of an organization depends on the orientation of all parts of the organization in line with the strategic direction of the organization. But complementarities of strategy and the culture of the organization have a special importance. If the strategy of the organization has not the necessary harmony with its culture, the risk of business failure will increase. Researchers believe that the competencies of a community highly depend on many hardware and software infrastructure for implementing of the strategy, because the culture and its norms are considered the software infrastructure of every community.

The first comprehensive and scientific definition of culture was presented by Edward Burnett Tylor in 1871 and in his definition of anthropological writes about culture:" the complete concept of Culture or civilization is an intricate whole consisting of science, art, morals, law, customs and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of the community" (Sharifzadeh.2008,11).

It is often difficult to define the organizational culture due to its complex characteristics, because some parts of forms of culture are intangible and invisible. Despite these difficulties, it seems that most authors agree that organizational culture is central and pivotal point of performance of organization. In the meantime, one of the researchers emphasizes that the holy, gentle, easily unchanged organizational culture has a historical basis and has been established in aggregate (Hofsted, 1990; 37). Organizational culture is unique in each particular organization and consists of objective and subjective dimensions and is related to beliefs, traditions and nature and also is related to shared expectations about the life of organization(Shraydr et al., 2005; 44).

The methods of the research

The time of research in this method is sectional, the results of the research are applicative and objective and the method of the research is correlative-descriptive.

The statistical community of the research

The statistical community of the research is all employees of Company of Electricity Distribution of Sistan and Baluchestan.

Discussion and conclusion:

Testing of hypothesis

The main hypothesis is: Organizational culture has a significant impact on the organizational effectiveness. This hypothesis consists of 3 sub-hypotheses which we will test these hypotheses:

Testing of the first sub-hypothesis:

Tribal culture has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness,

H_0 = tribal culture has no significant effect on organizational effectiveness. $H_0: \beta = 0$

Tribal culture has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness. $H_1: \beta \neq 0=H_1$

Pearson test results are shown in following Table.

Table (1): Results of the Pearson test for the first hypothesis

The name of the Variable		Tribal culture
Organizational Effectiveness	Pearson's correlation coefficient	0/709 24%
	unilateral significance level	235
	number	

The resumption of table (1)

Statistics Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Skewness	Elongation	Minimum	maximum
Tribal culture	3/01	0/1390	-0/188	0/293	1	5

As it can be seen in table, because unilateral significance level (0/24) is smaller than 5%, Hypothesis of H0 will be rejected. In other words, we can say with confidence of 95% that tribal culture has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness.

According to the obtained correlation coefficient of (0/293), the impact of tribal culture on organizational effectiveness is strong, direct and significant and in another words, if the dominant culture is in the form of the tribal culture, the organizational effectiveness will be enhanced.

Testing of the second sub-hypothesis

Hierarchical culture has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness.

H0 = Hierarchical culture has no significant impact on organizational effectiveness. H0: $\beta = 0$

H1: $\beta \neq 0$ Hierarchical culture has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness. = H1

Pearson test results are shown in following Table.

Table (2): Results of the Pearson test for the second sub-hypothesis

The name of the Variable		Hierarchical culture
Organizational Effectiveness	Pearson's correlation coefficient unilateral significance level number	0/649- 0/000 235

The resumption of table (2)

Statistics Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Skewness	Elongation	Minimum	maximum
Hierarchical culture	3/42	0/11183	-0/143	0/153	1	5

As it can be seen in table, because unilateral significance level (0/000) is smaller than 5%, Hypothesis of H0 will be rejected. In other words, we can say with confidence of 95% that hierarchical culture has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness.

According to the obtained correlation coefficient of (-0/649), the impact of hierarchical culture on organizational effectiveness is strong, reverse and significant and in another words, if the dominant culture is not in the form of the hierarchical culture, the organizational effectiveness will be enhanced.

Testing of the third sub-hypothesis

Market culture has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness.

H0 = Market culture has no significant effect on organizational effectiveness. H0: $\beta = 0$

Market culture has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness. H1: $\beta \neq 0=H1$

Pearson test results are shown in following Table.

Table (3): Results of the Pearson test for the third sub-hypothesis

The name of the Variable		Marketl culture
Organizational Effectiveness	Pearson's correlation coefficient unilateral significance level number	0/863 0/001 235

The resumption of table (3)

Statistics Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Skewness	Elongation	Minimum	maximum
Market culture	3/98	0/2146	-0/356	0/047	1	5

As it can be seen in table, because unilateral significance level (0/001) is smaller than 5%, Hypothesis of H0 will be rejected. In other words, we can say with confidence of 95% that market culture has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness.

According to the obtained correlation coefficient of (0/863), the impact of market culture on organizational effectiveness is strong, direct and significant and in another words, if the dominant culture is in the form of the market culture, the organizational effectiveness will be enhanced.

Conclusion

Culture is the indicator of the developing and implementing of strategy and provides a background for the organization to pursue its strategies. So harmony and compatibility must be among the culture, strategy and organization. Culture is formed by two types of beliefs, they are: the indicator beliefs which the organization is based on them and is philosophic and principle roots and the every day's beliefs which are the rules and feelings relating to everyday behavior. From the view of a systematic approach, the culture is the input of organization which directs the strategy and the performance of the organization is its output. Situations may be occurred that the preferred strategy is consistent with the organization's culture and society. In such a situation with regard to values, beliefs and norms simply do not provide the ability to perform actions related to strategy, strategy should be changed.

The main goal of this study is studying of the impact of organizational culture on organizational effectiveness; the statistical population of this research is employees of Company of Electricity Distribution of Sistan and Baluchestan who were selected as statistical sample through Morgan table. The method of data collection in theory is library method and in testing of hypotheses is survey method. The results of the research show that tribal culture and market have a significant and direct impact on organizational effectiveness and hierarchical culture also have an adverse effect on organizational effectiveness.

Suggestions

According to the results of the first sub-hypothesis based on the direct impact of tribal culture on organizational effectiveness, It will be recommended to the executive managers of the company of electricity distribution of Sistan and Baluchestan that provide conditions to increase the willingness and desire of the individual to interact with the surroundings effectively and experience opportunities to perform and express individual's capacity and they can be effective in increasing of effectiveness of the organization by specifying a reward for creative and innovative people in the company and also by providing conditions in which the experienced individuals, teach their skills to the other people and their colleagues.

According to the results of the second sub-hypothesis based on the direct impact of market culture on organizational effectiveness, It will be recommended to the executive managers of the company of electricity distribution of Sistan and Baluchestan that provide conditions to increase the willingness and desire of the individual to interact with the surroundings effectively and they also can be effective in increasing the effectiveness of the organization by using of the staff's ideas in making decisions and the creation of working groups for intimacy and communication.

According to the results of the third sub-hypothesis based on the reverse impact of hierarchical culture on organizational effectiveness, It will be recommended to the executive managers of the company of electricity distribution of Sistan and Baluchestan that the spirit of sincerity and honesty of employees to be strengthened by extending the power and freedom of action and by creating of group and teamwork spirit.

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